

SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF INTERNAL DISPLACEMENT

“A Case Study of Internally Displaced Persons from Federally Administered Tribal Areas to District Bannu”

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Abstract: Many cities around the country have experienced substantial population expansion in the recent two decades, with large arrivals from Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA) and Provincially Administered Tribal Areas (PATA). The militancy and military operations in certain areas were a well-known characteristic of this movement. The majority of the inhabitants, including women and children, came to Bannu and DI Khan from North and South Waziristan Agencies. This massive movement has a variety of economic, social, political, and environmental effects for the people who live in a given location. To determine the socioeconomic impact of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) on Bannu's host villages and to achieve the study's goal, essential factors such as law and order, crime rates, health and education, local property, and demand for products and services were chosen. The study is based on first-hand information. The study used two ways to analyse the data: descriptive statistics and a logistic regression model. Both data were evaluated, and it was shown that migration from North Waziristan has both a load and a benefit for the Bannu population. It has also been discovered that the cost of migration is disproportionately high for local hosts in comparison to the advantages. The data study found that basic facilities such as health and education were insufficient for the local people before the migration of IDPs, and that this issue became more acute with the presence of IDPs, affecting both the host communities and the IDPs. In addition, issues like as transportation, dacoits, and law and order situations have gotten worse. The cost of products and services increased, which had a negative impact on the local economy. In addition, the study discovered that IDPs' migration has positive consequences for their host communities. According to the research, the host benefited from the increase in the price of local property and prices.

Keywords : Internally Displaced Persons, Migration, Socio-economic, Tribal, Political, Crimes

1. Introduction

Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) are a group of people who are forced to leave their homes or places of residence due to natural catastrophes, social or armed conflict, military operations, and other factors, and who are forced to stay in other places but within their home country's borders. People who are compelled to leave their homes and relocate to other locations, such as camps, urban areas, or other villages, as a result of the aforementioned reasons are classified as IDPs.

Since 9/11, the United States' man-made disaster in Afghanistan has caused various issues for Pakistan. Airstrikes and clashes forced several militant groups to relocate to the safe and secure parts of Pakistan's tribal areas. Terrorist activities in various kinds have also crossed the borders since the arrival of those militant groups, posing a major security concern to Pakistan. These organisations sprung up along the Afghan-Pakistan border, including the Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA) and the Provincially Administered Tribal Areas (PATA), and they posed a severe internal danger to Pakistan's security and unity (Ullah & Malik, 2020).

The Pak army took serious actions against militant groups to combat militancy and provide internal security in order to restore peace in the region and to suppress the wave of terrorist activities, as well as to make Pakistan a safe and secure place for its citizens. The Pakistani army was involved in military operations in FATA and PATA. The fundamental purpose of those military actions was to keep the region peaceful and stable. Al-Mizan (2002-06) and other minor operations in South Waziristan agency, operation Rah Haq (2007), operation Zalzala (2008-09), and others in FATA, and operation Rah Rast (2009) in Swat (PATA) displaced a total of 746,700 people (Ullah & Malik, 2020). The majority of them who had just been displaced came from FATA, particularly Waziristan. Women and children made up 73 percent of the overall pool of displaced people from Waziristan. Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) relocated from so-called war zones to cities and camps in KP's settled areas (Kohat, Bannu, DI Khan) (IDPs). People from the terrorist-affected areas of Swat, Dir, Shangla, Bajaur Agency, and Buner relocated to Swabi, Mardan, Abbotabad, Haripur, Nowshera, Topi, and Peshawar's inhabited areas.

The term "host community" was coined by Sherlock (1999) to refer to a group of people residing in a single location. According to Aramberri (2001), a host community is a group of people who live on their own property. Williams and Lawson (2001) and Gursoyet al. (2002) defined the phrase as people from different backgrounds living in a specific area, or diverse groups living together in a specific geographical place, where they initially came from distinct backgrounds.

Various local and international NGOs, as well as the government, set up camps for IDPs in towns including as Peshawar, Lower Dir, DI Khan, Bannu, Tank, Nowshera, and Swabi, etc. However, most IDPs choose to remain in their families' homes due to common Pashtun traditions (Said, 2012). IDPs were housed in several ancient camps that had been created for Afghan refugees in 1972 (New Durani, Togh Serai camp, and Jalozaï camp). The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) compared the massive exodus from Swat in 2008-09 to the massive displacement from Rwanda in the 1990s. The key difference emphasised in the records is that only a small percentage of those displaced from Swat Valley were relocated to government and non-government-run camps. Obviously, the bulk stayed with relatives and friends in settled regions. According to UNICEF Director Louis-Georges Arsenault, "we encountered unparalleled humanitarian challenges in Pakistan, and it was significantly more difficult to reach with basic services because the vast majority of IDPs sought sanctuary with family or found protection in host communities outside the camps." Safe drinking water, transportation, sanitation, education, hospital overcrowding, and

other difficulties become serious problems for the host towns as well. The study was conducted under to evaluate the socio-economic impact of IDPs on host community in district Bannu and devise some practical solution for impact mitigation. The study is beneficial in the case that more than a million people have been forcibly displaced from their homes and native towns as a result of militancy or military operations in the aftermath of the 9/11 attacks, the greatest number since Pakistan's independence. This massive displacement is not only a significant issue for the many individuals who have been displaced, but it also has a variety of economic, social, political, and environmental effects and ramifications for the people who live in a particular location. There is a lot of study on IDPs-related topics in the literature, but only a small amount of research on the socio-economic impact of IDPs especially of that from FATA on host communities has been added to the literature so far.

2. Literature Review

Chambers (1986) investigated the influence of refugees on persons from various ethnic groups in the host community. He looked at how the host community benefits from the presence of refugees in the area. He concluded that the poor may suffer as a result of competition for services, food, and services. In a review study on the relationship between host communities and IDPs, the UN refugee agency UNHCR (1991) found that in majority of the literature, favourable and neutral attitudes about IDPs prevail. Few studies document IDPs' unfavourable patterns in the interaction between host communities and IDPs, which leads to their demonization. Furthermore, IDPs are blamed for the high cost of living and unemployment. Whitaker (2002) found in Western Tanzania on the relationship between refugee and host communities and found that settling refugees in camps causes a lot of issues such as prostitution and social promiscuity. In addition, the area's crime rate, robbery, and homicides are on the rise. His research also discovered that the refugees loot the host towns with the help of locals. When huge numbers of refugees migrate to the host community, Sanjuga (2002) studied huge migration and found that issue related to religion, ethnicity, and language arise. She recognised this type of impact in communities in Tanzania and Pakistan. She went on to say that they are the world's two largest refugee-hosting countries. Martin (2005) found that high numbers of refugees can impose a strain on natural resources, resulting in ecological and societal consequences. According to Black and Sessay (1997), resource demand drives the creation of settlements, resulting in firewood gathering, forest farm land conversion, fishing, hunting, and surface and ground water exploitation. Marion Coudrey (2008) did a study on Burmese displaced people. A sample of 800 displaced people was selected and was questioned in each camp to learn about the impact of government financial aid funding on their lives. The aid funds have received a good response from 65 percent of respondents. While 24% answer negatively, indicating an ineffective mechanism for financial distribution. Only 11% of respondents said it had no substantial impact on their lives. The findings of the study point to a positive outcome. In North Waziristan, Bile et al. (2010) found difficulties connected to health situations among internally displaced people. Several IDP camps in the Bannu district were chosen. The information was gathered from a variety of governmental and semi-governmental organisations. Essential medicines were needed in the 26 targeted health institutions in Bannu, Hangu, and Peshawar districts, according to a gap analysis of the public supply chain. Major health risks, such as medicine shortages and infectious illness outbreaks, as well as environmental health dangers, are identified in the report. The research recommends various health goals, including the provision of primary health-care services and the strengthening of overburdened health-care systems. Din (2010) looked at the impact of internal displacement in Pakistan

and found that it has a huge impact that demands quick support. Aside from emergency response, support should focus on IDPs' individual needs, such as health care, education, housing, and other basic necessities. Finger (2011) looked at the types of aid given to IDPs and concluded that not enough has been done. Children, women, and some minorities, according to the study, demand special care in terms of education and health. Grindheim (2013) investigated the impact of IDPs on host communities and divided it into two categories. The availability of health and education services to the host community has improved, which has had a positive socioeconomic impact. As a result of the influx of refugees into the host community, the market grows as demand rises owing to the increased population in the area. The number of project-based jobs increases for the host towns, resulting in an increase in employment. Conflicts between host communities and IDPs are among the negative consequences. The implications of displaced people's temporary shelters along the Thai-Myanmar border were investigated by Suwattana et al., (2015). There were a total of nine temporary shelters chosen. Three were chosen for further investigation. A range of study approaches were utilised at each of these shelters to examine the impact of displaced people's temporary shelters on the surrounding community. Observation (fieldtrips to each of the shelters), surveys, in-depth interviews, focus group sessions, and desk research were used to collect data. Members of the local community and local government authorities were among the respondents. According to the study, displaced people's temporary shelter has a negative impact on the local community. Security assurance, long-term safety, integrity, right to dignity, access to basic health facilities, and education were the core rights of IDPs, according to Javaid (2016), but the ground realities demonstrate that these aims are still a wish list.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Data and Method

In this part of the research paper, it explores that how the questionnaire and research questions were designed, how the data were collected? What strategy was used for data collection? What statistical methods, model and statistical software were utilized for analysis purpose?

3.2 Data Collection Tool

After conferring with researchers and reviewing relevant literature, a questionnaire was devised to obtain in-depth and primary information from the respondents. To obtain objective information, the most relevant closed ended questions were included, such as personal information of the respondents, population of that specific research area, access to clean drinking water, education and health, crime and security status, pressure on transportation, and impact of local business. We had added an item on "Impact of household budget on host communities" in the first copy of our questionnaire. However, after conducting the pilot study, we received no significant comments about the impact of IDP inflows on household budgets. Because, in the early days of IDPs' movement to district Bannu, certain families hosted IDPs in their homes, and the majority of IDPs had to make do with rented housing. Furthermore, some IDPs families who were live with host families were able to relocate to rented houses or government-run camps within months. As a result of the lack of meaningful answers from the host communities to this area of the questionnaire during our pilot project, we decided to remove the item on "Impact on household budget" from the questionnaire. Then, based on the results of the pilot study, we completed our questionnaire and performed a survey to obtain the necessary data.

3.3 Population of the study

Because most IDPs migrated from North Waziristan Agency and Frontier Region (FR) Bannu to district Bannu during militancy and military operations, the study's sampling population was the entire district Bannu. Data was collected from all segments of society with the use of developed questions to show the socio-economic impact on host communities.

3.4 Sampling methods and sample size

A total of seventy people were chosen at random from the entire population. Purposive sampling was used in this study because the researcher intended to interview people who were relevant to the research topic. The data collecting took about two months. Shopkeepers, self-employed people, police officers, doctors and pharmacists, teachers and principals of public and private schools and universities filled out the questionnaire.

3.5 Statistical Methods and Logistic Regression Model

For the purpose of producing relevant results, the data acquired through the questionnaire was carefully tallied in Microsoft Excel and then transferred to the statistical software SPSS. The researcher used a linear regression model to determine the association between the response variable and the predictors. If the following fundamental assumptions are met, the linear regression analysis is valid:

- i) The dependent variable must be a continuous variable.
- ii) The dependent variable must fulfill the assumption of normality.
- iii) The dependent variable may take negative values..
- iv) The residual term must be independently and identically distributed.

We can't use Simple Linear Regression Analyses if the preceding fundamental assumptions aren't met (SLRA). If the dependent variable is replaced by a categorical variable, the assumption is no (I). The SLRA (Simple Linear Regression Analyses) can't be trusted. In this scenario, the most appropriate statistical method for evaluating the relationship between a response and predictors is logistic regression. Unlike linear regression, logistic regression does not necessitate the use of precise assumptions.

The Logistic Regression Model can be written as.

$$\ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 HR_t + \beta_3 HF_t + \beta_3 CR_t + \beta_4 LS_t \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where in the above model $\ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right)$ is the odd ratio. Dependent variable is the anxiety of the respondents (host). While on the right hand side, we have independent variables i.e. House Rent (HR), Health Facilities (HF), Crime Rate (CR) and Law and order Situations (LS) $\beta_i = (\beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4)$ are the set of their coefficients. The two variables Health Facilities (HF) and Law and order Situations (LS) are given in likert scale are transformed from categorical variables (strongly disagree, disagree, **neutral**, **agree**, **strongly agree**) into binary variables (0 and 1) of whether the respondents disagree or agree with statement included in each variable. The other two variables rent of houses (HR) and crime rates (CR) are in binary form (1 for yes, 0

for no, or 1 for impact and 0 for no impact). The above association between response variable i.e. dichotomous and predictor allowed us to develop the logistic regression model.

For this regression the two steps must be fulfilled.

- (i) The probability value must be positive ($P \geq 0$).

$$P = \text{Exp}(\beta_1 + \beta_2 HR_t + \beta_3 HF_t + \beta_3 CR_t + \beta_4 LS_t) \text{ Eq. (2)}$$

$$P = e^{\beta_1 + \beta_2 HR_t + \beta_3 HF_t + \beta_3 CR_t + \beta_4 LS_t} \text{ Eq. (3)}$$

- (ii) In the second stage, it must be less than 1 ($P \leq 1$)

$$P = \frac{e^{\beta_1 + \beta_2 HR_t + \beta_3 HF_t + \beta_3 CR_t + \beta_4 LS_t}}{1 + e^{\beta_1 + \beta_2 HR_t + \beta_3 HF_t + \beta_3 CR_t + \beta_4 LS_t}} \text{ Eq. (4)}$$

This is also called the inverse function. It assumes that the predictor must not be related. It describes that a unit change in the variable HF is to change the log odds by β_3 . With the change in HF, the other variable must keep constant.

For further simplification, we rewrite Eq. (1)

$$\ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 HR_t + \beta_3 HF_t + \beta_3 CR_t + \beta_4 LS_t \text{ Eq. (5)}$$

This is logistic regression equation. The $\ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right)$ expression may be simplified as

$$P^* = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right)$$

Therefore,

$$P^* = \beta_1 + \beta_2 HR_t + \beta_3 HF_t + \beta_3 CR_t + \beta_4 LS_t \text{ Eq. (6)}$$

In Eq (5), the value of odds must be positive. Here the term “ln” is natural logarithm

4. Results and Discussion

The goal of this section is to determine the socioeconomic impact of IDPs on host communities. In the context of military operations in the region, Bannu district is being targeted as a host community for IDPs resulting from the migration of residents from North Waziristan. The information was gathered from residents in the Bannu district. The data was then tabulated in MS Excel before being analysed using SPSS software. The descriptive statistics and the Logistic regression model outputs are interpreted and analysed..

Table 1 Variables impacts

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Increased</i>	<i>Significantly Increased</i>	<i>Improved</i>	<i>worsened</i>
1. House Rent	--	↓(0.80)	--	--
2. School overcrowded	--	↓(0.90)	--	--
3. Epidemic Diseases	--	↓(0.81)	--	--
4. Crime Rates	--	↓(0.70)	--	--

5. Law & Order	--	↓(0.686)	--	--
6. Drug Uses	↓(0.50)	--	--	--
7. Public Transport	--	↓(0.95)	--	--
8. Profit to local business	--	↓(0.93)	--	--
9. Prices of goods & services	--	↓(0.70)	--	--
10. Property Business	--	↓(0.100)	--	--

Source: Author

*Epidemic Diseases: diarrhea, Malaria, respiratory diseases, infection etc

Crimes: Murders, thefts, dacoits, etc

Public transport: No of accidents, No of vehicles, travelling cost

Types of businesses: cooking, tailoring, driving, selling different products, haircutting, property business

In response to a question about house rent, 80% of respondents stated that house rent has increased significantly since the IDPs arrived in the area. 90% of respondents said that IDPs' movement inundated local schools, making it nearly impossible to build or expand new schools to accommodate their children in a short amount of time. As a result, the responsibility of the IDPs' children moved to the local community. Similarly, the available health facilities were also shared with the migrants; when asked if they had enough access to health care prior to the inflow of IDPs, 81 percent of respondents agreed that they did. These results are in line with the findings of Grindheim (2013).

After the massive migration to district Bannu, the offered results summarise the situation of security and crime rates in the locality. When asked about crime, 84.3 percent of respondents agreed that crimes such as murders, thefts, and dacoits, abduction, drug trafficking, and smuggling have increased in recent years. Similarly, 68 percent of respondents said the law and order situation in district Bannu had deteriorated, and 51 percent said drug use had increased as a result of the migration. Public transportation was overloaded, and the cost of travel increased, which had a direct impact on the residents of the Bannu district. In response to questions about local business, property business, and prices of goods and services, 93 percent of respondents said that the IDPs' migration benefited local businesses, that property business increased by nearly 100 percent, and that 70 percent of respondents agreed that prices of goods and services increased as a result of the IDPs' arrival in the district.

4.1 Logistic Regression Results

The findings of logistic regression are shown and summarised in the table below. The results illustrate the impact of several independent variables such as health, crime rate, and law and order conditions on the dependent variable, i.e. the respondents' anxiety in the host towns. The proper degrees of freedom are described in the following table, as well as the odd ratio of each covariate, as well as its interpretation and effect on the predictors.

Table 2: Logistic Regression Model

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<i>Variables</i>	<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>S.E</i>	<i>Wald</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Exp(B)</i>
House Rent				3.259	3	.353	
	α_1	-.950	.776	1.500	1	.021	0.387
	α_2	-1.284	.780	2.708	1	.100	.277
	α_3	.110	1.124	.010	1	.0622	1.116
Health Facility	β	-.524	1.135	.213	1	.0644	.592
Crime	γ	-.177	1.260	.020	1	.0889	.838
Law & Order Situation	Ψ	-.045	.038	1.355	1	.144	.956
Constant	η	.177	1.342	.017	1	.895	1.194

Variable(s): House Rent, Health Facility, Crime, and Law& Order Situation.

The estimates demonstrate a monotonic influence of house rent on respondents' anxiety. The odds of respondents receiving less rent having anxiety are higher on average than the comparable odds for respondents receiving more rent. Although the inflow of IDPs has similar consequences on the host community, certain members of the host community are compensated, such as those who receive higher rents for rental dwellings that they rent to IDPs. Those who pay less rent for their rented housing are disproportionately affected by the influx of IDPs.

Similarly, the estimate demonstrates that the health facility has a significant impact on respondents' worry. Anxiety is more common among responders who have fewer health facilities than among those who have more health facilities. In terms of access to health facilities, the Bannu district's host community can be divided into two groups: those who have more access to health facilities and those who have less access to health services. Our findings imply that host communities with higher access to health services are less affected by IDP inflows than those with fewer health facilities.

The estimations reveal that crime has a monotonic influence on respondents' worry. Anxiety levels are higher on average among respondents who are confronted with more crimes than among those who are confronted with fewer crimes. As long as crime rates rise in tandem with the influx of IDPs, psychological strain on communities rises, and residents fear becoming victims of crime. However, the communities can be divided into two categories in this instance as well. Those who live in locations where crime rates are higher than those who live in areas where crime rates are not as high. As a result, the likelihood of anxiousness is higher among them. Similarly, the estimate reveals that the Law & Order Situation has a significant impact on respondents' anxiety. Anxiety is more common among individuals who are less protected than it is among those who are more protected. The most vulnerable sector is law and order, which is exacerbated by the influx of IDPs. The entry of IDPs has no less negative impact on better protected host communities than it does on less protected host communities.

The findings showed that the influx of IDPs had put a lot of pressure on the water in the area. The majority of residents in the area drink tap water from domestic wells or hand pumps. Water is already scarce, and

with the influx of IDPs, the locals will undoubtedly have to share it with the IDPs. As a result, it proved difficult for both locals and IDPs to manage clean drinking water. Despite this, the local administration found it extremely difficult to secure an alternate source of pure water. As a result, ensuring the availability of safe drinking water was difficult. Water scarcity, according to Homer-Dixon (1991), exacerbates social conflict between IDPs and host communities. It was also pointed out by the Black (1993) that the shortage of water may create conflicts between host and IDPs. Therefore, our results and the related literature it is concluded that IDPs arrival has extreme negative impact on water resources.

The massive migration from North Waziristan had serious consequences for host communities in the district of Bannu's education sector. It's also crucial to note that district Bannu is a developing metropolis in KP. The quality of education has been improving. Many private schools, as well as new universities, medical and engineering institutes, have been built. Many students from North Waziristan, the Frontier Region of Bannu, and even other parts of the KP come to Bannu to enrol in schools and colleges. The existing educational institutions, particularly schools, were already overburdened, but the sudden and massive influx exacerbated the issue. According to our results, 90 percent of the responded accepted that the schools are overcrowded because IDPs have also started to send their children especially to the government schools. It has adverse implications in the domain of education standard and imposed a very high cost on the host community.

4.2 Access to health/Medicare

According to our descriptive analysis, 82% of respondents strongly agreed that the current healthcare services for the host population are insufficient. There are three main hospitals in the city: the District Head Quarter (DHQ) Teaching Hospital, the Khalifa Gul Nawaz (KGN) Teaching Hospital, and the Zanana Teaching Hospital, as well as Basic Health Units (BHUs) in villages throughout the district of Bannu, which provide medical services not only to Bannu residents, but also to people from North Waziristan and FR Bannu. The presence of IDPs in Bannu city and surrounding villages put a lot of strain on these facilities. IDPs who were vulnerable arrived in bad health. Similarly, the logistic regression model reveals that respondents with fewer health facilities are more anxious than those with more health facilities. As a result, we can conclude, based on both descriptive analysis and the logistic regression model, that host communities with more health facilities are less affected by the inflow of IDPs than those with less health facilities.

4.3 Crimes and Security

As IDPs relocated to the district of Bannu, social turmoil such as murders, theft and burglary, smuggling, and other social difficulties increased. When indicated in the descriptive statistics results, the majority of the host community respondents admitted that as migrants from the agency arrived, murders and thefts increased in the area. Furthermore, host communities feel frightened as a result of host-IDP disputes. Homer-Dixon (1991), a theorist, identified that population growth is linked to an increase in conflict. When diverse cultural and ethnic groups coexist, he believes, it fosters hatred between them. UNHCR study also found that the refugees' migration in the place of asylum creates serious political security

confusion among the host community (UNHCR, 2006). Loescher (1992) investigated that the movement of refugees create a great threat to the harmony of the population. The logistic regression model also implies that protected host populations are less vulnerable to crime. The results of our logistic regression model match those of descriptive statistics. The coefficient estimates demonstrate that the odds of worry are higher among respondents who are encountering more crimes on average than among respondents who are facing less crime. As long as crime rates rise in tandem with the influx of IDPs, psychological strain on communities rises, and residents fear becoming victims of crime. As a result, both the descriptive analysis and the logistic regression model show that the healer is effective.

4.4 Population of the locality

After the military operation in North Waziristan and FR Bannu, people began migrating to district Bannu. Women, children, elderly, and young people, as well as their animals and luggage, were relocated to Bannu. Because of the presence of their close family and acquaintances, almost everyone chooses to settle in Bannu city or adjacent villages. The proximity to their native place was also a crucial element in their choices. The most serious problem that displaced individuals face is the lack of rental housing, which forces most families to live in tents. This massive migration was the primary reason of the abrupt increase in population density. Many of them initially settled with relatives and friends, which had a significant impact on their monthly budget and caused enormous problems such as hygiene, room provision, child care, harassment, and other issues for the district's residents, in addition to general issues such as waterborne diseases, education-related issues, and a slew of other issues that negatively impacted the district's residents.

4.5 Impact on local business

The study's most notable characteristic is the sudden increase in aggregate demand for goods and services. According to theory, population is the most important factor of aggregate demand. According to our findings, nearly 90% of respondents agreed that local businesses grew during and after the arrival of IDPs in their community. As the aggregated demand curves shift rightwards, other elements such as price level rise; similarly, our findings revealed that as aggregate demand rose, price levels rose as well, and people's purchasing power decreased. When demand spikes unexpectedly, more entrepreneurs are drawn in from both within and outside the area.

4.6 Pressure on transport and conveyance

Overcrowding was another concern related with the displaced folks that had a severe impact on the host community's well-being. According to the findings of the study, a large number of respondents (95.7 percent) claimed that transportation has become a major issue as residents from North Waziristan agency and FR Bannu relocated to the district of Bannu. As more people arrived in the area, the government granted permission for Non-Custom Paid (NCP) automobiles, which boosted traffic congestion.

5. Conclusion and Policy Implications

5.1 Conclusion

The impact of IDPs on host communities in the Bannu district was explored in this study. The goal was to reveal the nature of any problems that may have arisen as a result of the influx of IDPs into the district. Both descriptive statistics and regression analysis approaches were used to quantify this goal. A questionnaire was created in the initial step, followed by the pilot study. After deleting some unnecessary items, the questionnaire was completed.

The relationship between Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) from North Waziristan and the host communities of district Bannu has been developed as a result of the research findings. The study's major goal is to demonstrate the socioeconomic impact of IDPs on host communities in Bannu area. The migration of IDPs has had more negative than positive consequences on the socio-economic situations of host communities, according to our findings. The study is primary in nature, hence descriptive statistics and a logistic regression model were used to determine the impact of internally displaced persons on the socioeconomic structure of district Bannu residents. The results of descriptive statistics and a logistic regression model revealed that the enormous influx of IDPs had a detrimental impact on district Bannu's native hosts. It was discovered that the large migration had a significant impact on practically all aspects of host communities, including education, health, law and order, crime, transportation, pricing of products and services, housing rents, and Bannu residential and commercial property. According to our results, the district's education sector has been hit hard by this massive movement. Because IDPs began to send their children to government schools, the burden on educational institutions worsened the quality of education. Furthermore, it has been discovered that existing healthcare resources, such as hospitals and basic health units, are insufficient for the local hosts, and that the influx of a large number of IDPs has put significant strain on those hospitals and BHUs. As IDPs flocked to the Bannu, social turmoil including as murders, thefts, smuggling, and other social difficulties increased. This movement has a substantial impact on the cost of products and services. With the increase in the price of goods and services, the situation for the poor people in the host communities got more difficult. Our findings also revealed the advantages of IDP migration. The study discovered that the sudden increase in population enhanced demand for goods and services, resulting in increased local business. With the unexpected increase in demand, more entrepreneurs were attracted from both inside the same area as well as from the surrounding areas. Finally, we may say that the massive migration imposed both a cost and a benefit on the host communities. However, the costs outweigh the advantages by a large margin.

1. We noted in the analysis section how both IDPs and the host community have been severely impacted by the crises that have arisen in the area as a result of the influx of IDPs. The Pakistani government, as well as national and international NGOs, must concentrate not only on issues concerning IDPs, but also on developing programmes and policies that benefit the host community.
2. As we saw in the analytical part, the health sector has deteriorated significantly. The host community is dissatisfied with the health services that are presently accessible. The main focus of national and international organisations is internally displaced persons (IDPs). The host community has been

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ignored, and no incentives have been given in exchange for the services that the host communities have offered to the IDPs. As a result, it is critical to strengthen the deteriorating health sector so that both IDPs and hosts can benefit from these services..

3. 3. The education industry was another crucial area that had a considerable impact. As IDPs arrived in the district, the number of students in primary and secondary schools exploded. The number of students per instructor grew, which had an indirect impact on educational quality. Second, the furniture that was offered was insufficient to accommodate those students. To simplify these concerns, timely provision of these amenities was not supplied to these people; as a result, it became expensive for everyone.
4. The transport sector was one of the primary repercussions of the influx of IDPs. The transportation sector problem is a long-term issue that is difficult to address in the short run. However, the government's actions in dealing with this issue are commendable. IDPs have been given permission to operate their non-custom paid (NCP) vehicles in the Bannu district, which is a settled region. This made it easier for IDPs to transfer their family and directly lessened the negative impact on local transportation in the district. IDPs gained a source of income as a result of this.
5. In terms of education, the government took some practical initiatives to relieve the burden of IDP children on host communities, such as admitting IDP children to normal government schools such as federal government (FG) schools and Army public schools (APS) throughout Pakistan. The educational institutes in Bannu district were relieved of their burden as a result of this initiative. Similar activities are also advised in the fields of employment creation for IDPs, health care, and housing arrangements, among other things.
6. The IDPS, as described in the results, lacks new or necessary skills. They couldn't start new businesses or economic activity. Unemployment is also at an all-time high. The market was unable to absorb the current labour force, and the addition of IDPs has exacerbated the situation. The host community suffers unfavourable consequences as a result of these crises. Neither the Pakistani government nor any other agency or institution attempted to address the problem. Making job-oriented policies is the government's and other national organisations' primary task.

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